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STUDY OF STATIC AND CLASSICAL DEFINITION OF PROBABILITY, THEIR DIFFERENCES

Assoc. Prof. **H.K.Abdurakhmanova**,
assistant **Sh.U.Toshpulatova**
student **B.L.Khatamova**
Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry

ANNOTATION

This article examines the classical and statistical approaches to probability. Probability plays a key role in science, technology, and daily life, helping to predict events and analyze risks. We will explore the applications and differences of these two approaches.

Keywords: *probability, mathematics, Blaise Pascal, science and technology.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматриваются классический и статистический подходы к вероятности. Вероятность играет важную роль в науке, технике и жизни, помогая предсказывать события и анализировать риски. Мы изучим их применение и основные различия.

Ключевые слова: *вероятность, математика, Блез Паскаль, наука и техника*

Reliability plays a key role in various scientific, technical, economic and everyday life. It helps to predict events, analyze risks and make informed decisions. In mathematics, there are several approaches to defining probability, two of which are classical and statistical. In this article we will look at both definitions, their applications and the main differences. Classical probability was proposed in the 17th century by

mathematicians such as Blaise Pascal and Pierre de Fermat. It is used in cases where all possible outcomes of a random experiment are equally probable. The classical definition of probability is convenient in cases where all outcomes are known in advance and equally probable. It is widely used in combinatorics, games and theoretical calculations. However, in real situations, especially in science and technology, one often has to work with data obtained from observations and experiments. If there are n equally probable outcomes possible in an experiment, and event A can occur in m of them, then the probability of event A is defined as:

$$P(A) = \frac{m}{n}$$

Task 1: A textile factory produces fabric in five different colors: red, blue, green, white, and black. Each batch of fabric has an equal chance of being one of these colors. What is the probability that a randomly selected batch will be blue?

Solution: Since all colors occur with equal probability, the total number of possible outcomes is 5 (according to the number of different colors of fabric). A favorable outcome is choosing blue fabric, there are 1 such outcomes. We use the classical probability formula:

$$P(\text{blue}) = \frac{\text{number of favorable outcomes}}{\text{total number of outcomes}} = \frac{1}{5} = 0,2(\text{or } 20\%).$$

Answer: The probability that the selected batch will be blue is 0.2 or 20%.

Task 2: A textile manufacturing warehouse contains 8 rolls of cotton fabric and 12 rolls of linen fabric. A worker randomly selects one roll. What is the probability that the roll selected is cotton?

Solution : The total number of possible outcomes is the total number of rolls of fabric: 8 (cotton) + 12 (linen) = 20 rolls. A favorable outcome is the choice of a cotton roll, there are 8 such outcomes. We use the classical probability formula:

$$P(\text{cotton}) = \frac{\text{number of favorable outcomes}}{\text{total number of outcomes}} = \frac{8}{20} = 0,4(\text{or } 40\%).$$

Answer: The probability that the selected roll will be cotton is 0.4 or 40%

Statistical probability allows us to estimate the probability of events in the real world by analyzing the frequency of their occurrence. This method is especially useful

in situations where it is impossible to determine in advance the exact number of possible outcomes or when probabilities change over time. If an event E occurs m times out of n trials, then its probability is calculated using the formula:

$$P(E) = \frac{m}{n}$$

Real observations: Statistical probability is widely used to analyze the results of experiments and observations in cases where it is impossible or impractical to assume that all outcomes are equally likely.

Risk assessment and forecasting: Used in economics, medicine, engineering and other fields to estimate the probabilities of events based on historical data.

Thus, statistical probability allows us to obtain approximate values of probabilities based on actual data and experiments, which is especially important in practical applications where experimental conditions may deviate from ideal.

Task 1: A textile factory conducted quality control. Of 1,000 rolls of fabric tested, 25 were found to be defective. What is the statistical probability that a randomly selected roll will be defective?

Solution: Number of tests (total number of rolls) — $n = 1000$.

Number of favorable outcomes (defective rolls) — $m = 25$.

According to the statistical probability formula:

$$P(\text{defective roll}) = \frac{m}{n} = \frac{25}{1000} = 0,025$$

Answer: The probability of selecting a defective roll is 0.025 (or 2.5%).

Task 2: The factory warehouse has shipped 5,000 rolls of fabric in the last month. Of these:

- 2200 rolls of white color,
- 1500 rolls of black color,
- 800 rolls of blue color,
- 500 rolls of red color,

A customer orders a roll at random from those shipped. What is the statistical probability that the customer will receive a black roll?

Solution: The total number of shipped rolls is $n = 5000$.

The number of favorable outcomes (black rolls) is $m = 1500$.

According to the formula of statistical probability:

$$P(\text{black roll}) = \frac{m}{n} = \frac{1500}{5000} = 0,3$$

Answer: The probability that a customer will receive a black roll is 0.3 (or 30%).

Comparison of classical and statistical probability

Characteristic	Classical probability	Statistical probability
Definition	Based on the assumption that all outcomes are equally likely	Determined by the results of experiments
Formula	$P(E) = (\text{number of favorable outcomes}) / (\text{total number of possible outcomes})$	$P(E) = (\text{number of occurrences of event E}) / (\text{total number of trials})$
Applicability	Used in theoretical problems (dice, cards, coins)	Used in real research, statistics, experiments
Example	The probability of getting a 6 on a fair dice is: $P(6) = 1/6$	After 100 throws of the dice, "6" came up 18 times $\rightarrow P(6) = 18/100 = 0.18$
Addiction to Experiments	Does not depend on experience, based on logical analysis	Depends on the number of experiments and real observations
Variability	Fixed for ideal conditions	May vary depending on experimental conditions.
Connection	It is a limiting case of statistical probability with an infinite number of trials	With a large number of experiments, it approaches classical probability (the law of large numbers)

Thus, both definitions of probability complement each other and are applied depending on the context of the problem.

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